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**Implementation of a PAB incl. terms of
reference, mandate and scope of the board**

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Publishable Summary

[EU-PolarNet 2](#) strives to provide policy advice in response to questions related to the Polar Regions from the European Commission and other decision makers at national and regional levels. To fulfil this objective, *EU-PolarNet 2* establishes a Policy Advisory Board as point of contact for advice based on national expertise. The role of the Policy Advisory Board is to provide up-to-date, evidenced-based, explicit and implementable recommendations, advice or briefings on Polar-related questions on behalf of the whole European Polar community. This document contains the Terms of Reference (ToR) for the Policy Advisory Board.

Preamble

Rationale and Setting

The consequences of climate warming are extremely well visible in the Arctic and are significantly noticeable in Antarctica. An increased awareness of such changes impacting both Polar Regions stimulate a high interest and new initiatives of the European Commission (EC) and the EU member countries leading to better understanding of natural, social and economic processes. Thus, such processes have driven a need for timely and accurate advice on how these new circumstances change in practice for polar actors.

One of the main tasks of *EU-PolarNet 2* is utilise its network of researchers and stake- and rightholders to implement an up-to-date, evidence-based, explicit policy advice. The advice shall provide answers to questions about issues related to both Polar Regions. For this purpose, *EU-PolarNet 2* will establish a Policy Advisory Board (PAB) within the project governance structure (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Illustration of the [governance of EU-PolarNet 2](#) including its different boards. Solid arrows show reporting flows and dashed arrows the feedback flows. The PAB is an important part of the management level of *EU-PolarNet 2* and will interact directly with the Executive Board.

Scope and role of the Policy Advisory Board (PAB)

The PAB's scope is to guarantee evidence-based policy advice to the EC and other decision-makers through *EU-PolarNet 2*. It will support *EU-PolarNet 2* in its relationship with the EC and other policy makers and it will provide evidence-based advice on pressing issues related to the Polar Regions.

The PAB will consist of one representative per *EU-PolarNet 2* partner who should have an in-depth overview of the expertise in their national community. This PAB members do not need to be experts in a specific discipline but shall know which national expert they can address to get advice.

The PAB has the following roles:

- to provide policy advice on issues related to the Polar Regions on an ad-hoc basis,
- to respond to requests from *EU-PolarNet 2*, and through *EU-PolarNet 2* from the EC and other national policy makers, to issues related to the Polar Regions,
- to consult with national Polar experts, for the benefit of EU and national policymakers,
- to support *EU-PolarNet 2* in identifying important topics and speakers for the planned policy briefings.

Difference between the Policy Advisory Board and the Polar Expert Group (PEG)

The Polar Expert Group (PEG) will be comprised of internationally recognised experts in all kinds of Polar Research including representatives from the [EU Polar Cluster](#) projects, Indigenous researchers and researchers from business, NGO's or further stakeholders performing research in the Polar Regions. It belongs to WP3 and is a scientific expert forum. The role of the PEG is to assist WP3 in the research prioritisation process by specifying and customising the research needs recommended in the [European Polar Research Programme](#) and the *EU-PolarNet 1* White papers (see [D3.1](#) for further information).

Terms of Reference (ToR) of the EU-PolarNet 2 Policy Advisory Board

T.1 Scope of the PAB

The scope of the PAB is to provide up-to-date, evidence-based, straightforward, and implementable recommendations, advice or briefings on questions related to both Polar Regions from the European Commission and European national policy makers.

T.2 Membership of the PAB

The PAB shall consist of maximum 25 members. They will be nominated by the *EU-PolarNet 2* partners. Potential PAB members shall have a very good knowledge of their national polar communities to be able to reach out to appropriate experts. Members from various stakeholder groups might be also included if nominated by the *EU-PolarNet 2* partners. PAB members can also be recruited from the *EU-PolarNet 2* project partners, since not too many persons have the necessary overview of the national expertise and many of them represent their country already in *EU-PolarNet 2*. All PAB members including the chairs serve as volunteers (not compensated) for defined terms of 2 years, which may be renewed. Travel and subsistence costs for PAB meetings (if organised) will be compensated.

Membership criteria

- Each partner nominates not more than one expert as their national delegate to the PAB.
- PAB members have a good overview of their national polar research strategies and communities.
- PAB members will be the point of contact for advice based on national expertise.

Nomination of the PAB members

- Every *EU-PolarNet 2* partner may nominate the most appropriate expert according to its inner national procedure.
- The submission of nominations for the PAB members has to be done using the PAB membership form enclosed as the Annex 1.
- Each appointed candidate for the PAB must consent to the candidacy and disclose any potential financial or scientific/professional conflicts of interest (see: T.5 Transparency and conflict of interest management).
- In accepting the membership in the EU-PolarNet 2 Policy Advisory Board (PAB), the expert agrees to be confined by the Terms of Reference (ToR).

Appointment and review of the PAB members

- Members are appointed by the *EU-PolarNet 2* General Assembly after review by the EU-PolarNet 2 Executive Board.
- The General Assembly of the *EU-PolarNet 2* will review the membership and composition of the PAB every year to ensure it meets with the requirements of the ToR.
- If a PAB member no longer meets the requirements then his/her membership shall cease,

and the vacancy shall be filled by appointment by the *EU-PolarNet 2* partner.

T.3 Organisation of the PAB

The PAB's governance team comprises a chair, a deputy chair and an executive secretary.

The PAB chairs are elected by the Board members and endorsed by the *EU-PolarNet 2* General Assembly. The PAB will elect the chairs and deputy chair from its members by a simple majority vote. The chair and the deputy chair must be from different institutions/countries.

Chair

Duties

- The chair will oversee an efficient and effective work of the PAB in accordance with the ToR.
- In fulfilling these duties, the chair will use best endeavours to act independently in pursuance of any legal or regulatory requirements.
- In particular, the chair (with the assistance of the executive secretary) shall ensure that the PAB conducts its work in accordance with the requirements of EU regulations and *EU-PolarNet 2* needs.

Appointment

- The chair will be elected from the PAB members by a simple majority vote and finally endorsed by the *EU-PolarNet 2* General Assembly.
- Relevant experience/criteria for a candidate include:
 - Broad overview about the national expertise in polar – related topics,
 - Ability to represent interests of *EU-PolarNet 2* and polar actors to external bodies (European Commission, other international or national bodies and media),
 - Reputation for fairness and integrity.

Termination

- The term of service of the Chair is two years, with the possibility of re-election for one more term.
- By notice from the *EU-PolarNet 2* coordinator and endorsed by the General Assembly, the chair may be removed from office if:
 - Ceases to fulfil the requirements of membership of the PAB,
 - Becomes incapable of performing the functions of the office as outlined in the ToR whether by illness, infirmity, or incompetence,
 - Or is found by a properly constituted supervisory authority to have breached any law or regulation applicable to his/her professional role.

Deputy Chair

Duties

The deputy chair shall perform the function of the chair in the event of the chair's absence, incapacity or on an interim basis in the event of the chair's removal.

Appointment

The deputy chair will be elected by a simple majority vote from the appointed members of the PAB.

- Relevant experience/criteria:
 - Broad overview about the national expertise in polar – related topics,
 - Ability to represent *EU-PolarNet 2* and polar actors' interests to external bodies,
 - Reputation for fairness and integrity.

Termination

- The term of office of a deputy chair is two years, with the possibility of re-election for one more term.
- By notice from the *EU-PolarNet 2* coordinator and endorsed by the General Assembly, the deputy chair may be removed from office if:
 - ceases to fulfil the requirements of membership of the PAB,
 - becomes incapable of performing the functions of the office as outlined in the ToR whether by illness, infirmity, or incompetence,
 - or is found by a properly constituted supervisory authority to have breached any law or regulation applicable to his/her professional role.

Executive secretary

Duties

The executive secretary will be responsible for the efficient administration of the PAB including the convening of meetings, preparation and circulation of minutes, reporting, timely follow-up of agreed actions. The executive secretary shall ensure that members of the PAB comply with the ToR, bringing any potential breaches to the chair and the *EU-PolarNet 2* Executive Board's attention.

The executive secretary will bring to the chair of the PAB any policy issue received by the *EU-PolarNet 2* coordinator from the EU or any European national policy maker. The Executive Secretary will report recommendations or conclusions issued from the PAB to the *EU-PolarNet 2* coordinator for transmission.

Appointment

The executive secretary will be appointed from the Management Support Team.

T.4 Meetings

- PAB will fulfil its role by meeting on request of the coordinator. Meetings of the PAB will be conducted preferably remotely as videoconferences or by exchange of emails.

- The chair, or in his/her absence the deputy chair, shall preside the meetings.
- A copy of the draft minutes of every meeting of the PAB shall be sent as soon as practicable to every member of the PAB. The minutes remain in draft until adopted by the PAB.
- The quorum for a meeting of the PAB shall be more than half of its members.
- The Secretary shall prepare a half-year summary of the PAB work to report to the *EU-PolarNet 2* coordinator and the Executive Board. This summary report must be submitted in advance of the Executive Board meetings.
- The PAB chair shall report to the *EU-PolarNet 2* General Assemblies about the activities during the past year and current activities.
- Where it is deemed necessary, the PAB may set up an ad hoc subgroup to deal with specific topics and invite a limited number of members and co-opted external experts to participate. Such subgroups shall report back to the PAB with any recommendations, which will be considered by the PAB.

T.5 Transparency and conflict of interest management

Full transparency of potential financial and scientific conflicts is important to ensure the credibility of the process and the advice/recommendations by the PAB members.

The PAB is established with the aim of avoiding all potential professional and financial conflicts of interest among its officers and its board members. All potential board members are asked to disclose any potential financial or scientific/professional conflicts of interest. Disclosures must be made prior to the PAB member appointments and covering 1 year prior to initiation of work on the PAB.

Individuals are also asked to disclose funding of Polar research activities to their institutional division, department, or working group.

T.6 Evidence identification and collection

Guidance is to be developed using the expertise and experience of the PAB members with an evidence-based review of information that is largely available to Polar actors. Publications of research results in peer-reviewed journals and publications or presented at major international and national scientific conferences will be used. Additionally, reports or other material from the different Arctic and Antarctic international organizations and intergovernmental bodies and authorized national agencies will be referred to. Press releases, unpublished reports, and personal communications are generally not going to be taken into consideration.

T.7 Rating of the evidence and recommendations

The guidance is presented in the form of recommendations, advice or briefings. Each recommendation is rated in terms of the level of its evidence and strength. The PAB will define a scale of confidence of released recommendations. A summary of the supporting (and conflicting) evidence follows each recommendation or set of recommendations.

T.8 Data review, synthesis and preparation of recommendations with supporting information

Draft recommendations are developed by subgroups of the Board with interest and expertise in particular sections of the guidance. Following development of supporting text and references, the sections are reviewed both by the board and chairs. A penultimate draft is submitted to *EU-PolarNet 2* Executive Board for final review and approval before transmitting eventually as needed to *EU-PolarNet 2* partners, the European Commission or national policy makers.

Subgroups of the PAB may meet by teleconference as needed to update recommendations and supporting evidence. Updates may be prompted by new publications or presentations at major national or international scientific conferences, a new international agreement (or new indications, dosing formulations, or frequency of dosing), new Arctic Council and Antarctic Treaty decisions, or other information that may have a substantial impact on the European Polar Policy. Updates and changes in the guidance are indicated by highlighted text on the ad-hoc online site and a notice of update is posted on the *EU-PolarNet 2* homepage.

Annex 1. The PAB membership nomination form

Profile of the nominee to the Policy Advisory Board by the *EU-PolarNet 2* partner

Name of the nominate entity - the *EU-PolarNet 2* partner:

Given Name and Family Name of the nominee:

Affiliation:

Title / Position:

Field of expertise in polar activity:

Experience relating to the PAB membership:

Annex 2. Members of the Policy Advisory Board

Table: Confirmed members of the EU-PolarNet 2 Policy Advisory Board as of April 20, 2021, subject to change.

Affiliation	Surname	First Name	Position	Field of expertise in polar activity (not exhaustive)
Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany	Rachold	Volker	Head of German Arctic Office	International research coordination and science management in all aspects of Arctic research
Arctic Centre, University of Lapland	Ikävalko	Johanna	Director of the Arctic Centre, University of Lapland	Polar biology, Earth system science approach, engagement of Indigenous peoples, research funding, science policy, science communication
Institute of Polar Sciences (ISP), National Research Council of Italy (CNR)	Ademollo	Nicoletta	Researcher	Environmental chemistry, Ecotoxicology of persistent and emerging organic pollutants (POPs)
Norwegian Polar Institute	Koç	Nalân	Dr. / Research Director	Marine geology/paleoceanography, climate interpretations from polar oceans, head of Centre for Ice, Climate and Ecosystems (ICE)
European Polar Board	Badhe	Renuka	Executive Secretary	Polar oceanography; Polar policy and evidence-based advice; Strategy development, Horizon Scanning and Futures; Diversity in polar research
ICOMOS International Polar Heritage Committee (IPHC)	Barr	Susan	Dr / Executive member – Arctic Advisor / Independent researcher	Arctic and Antarctic cultural heritage conservation and protection, Polar history
Arctic Centre – University of Groningen	Scheepstra	Annette	Coordinator external cooperation	Stakeholder engagement, transdisciplinary research, Arctic social sciences
DAFSHE	Djørup	Stine	Senior Adviser	Science policy, research administration, research ethics, scientific integrity

CNRS	Ritz	Catherine	Dr. / Senior scientist	Glaciology, ice sheet modelling & climate feedbacks, ice-core geochemistry
Ministry of Education and Science, the Republic of Poland	Jałukowicz	Tomasz	Counsellor to the Minister	Expert from governmental decision making bodies on polar science and public policies in international politics and research projects facilitation
Bulgarian Antarctic Institute	Mateev	Dragomir	Coordinator of Science and Logistics	Logistic and scientific preparation of polar expeditions, scientific calls, reporting to the Ministry of Education and Science
University of Vienna, APRI	Richter	Andreas	Professor	Permafrost, Polar Ecology, Arctic Terrestrial Ecosystems, Permafrost Soils, Climate Change Feedbacks
Office of the President of the Republic of Estonia	Palo	Timo	Climate Policy Adviser to the President	Climate and environmental changes in polar regions, Polar exploration
Royal Greenland	Thinghuus	Mikael	CEO	Greenlandic fishing industry, Royal Greenland A/S company
Oceanwide Expeditions	van der Hulst	Mark	COO	Expedition style cruises to the Arctic, North Atlantic, Antarctic and Sub-Atlantic Islands
Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, University of Lisbon	Vieira	Goncalo	Associate Professor	Permafrost, Geomorphology, Cryosphere, Remote Sensing, Infrastructure, Programme coordination
UKRI-BAS	Francis	Jane	Professor Dame. Director of BAS	Palaeoclimatology and palaeobotany
ITU PoReC & TUBITAK MAM Polar Research Institute	Ozsoy	Burcu	Executive Board Member of ITU PoReC – Director Of TUBITAK MAM PRI	Satellite technology, statistical mathematics, geophysics, sea ice in-situ measurements, climate change, Antarctica, Arctic
University of Zurich	Schaepman-Strub	Gabriela	Prof Dr	Arctic terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystem functions, indigenous knowledge holders

RANNIS	Jonasson	Hallgrimur	General Director	Science-policy interface; management of Arctic science platforms; domestic and international funding mechanisms; geology
Spanish Polar Committee	Ramos	Sonia	Member of the secretariat	Antarctic Treaty System incl. Committee of Environmental Protection, Arctic management system